

Strange Case of Dr. Freud and Mr. Hyde

I'm fascinated by the last decades of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th. Some call the period that followed the end of the Franco-Prussian War in 1871, and continued until the eve of the fateful First World War, the "Belle Époque," which put an end to the dream of that era of great advances and enthusiasm for science and the arts – it was the era of the revolution of the Impressionist painters, a shift in the conception of the posture of art – and what could have been a world of increasing happiness, were it not for the frustration of the two World Wars that would shake this faith in such a beautiful world!

In this fascinating moment of consolidation, insinuation, or emergence of important forms of science, our Freudian psychoanalysis would emerge. But one detail that strikes me is that, by some "coincidence" that is far from fortuitous, before Dr. Freud published his concepts and theories, a work appeared in British literature whose content seems to me to be extremely related to elements of Freudian theory. Was it intuitive and somehow "premonitory"? As with "vates"? Soothsayers? This is also a term used to refer to poets, to artists guided by intuition...

It's the book "Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde," originally titled "Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde." The basis of the story is well known, so we can go straight to the commentary on why I find it fascinating that it was published before Freud's works. Because I believe that, in his own way, with creativity and artistic license, the author "captured in the air" the same spirit of the readings that, around the same time, were feeding Dr. Freud's scientific mind, although, in this case, with a much more rigorous bias than would occur to an artist; but he, in his own way, and immersed in the similar context of European society of his time, somehow, intuitively and artistically, foretold the presence, in the same person, of a part of their behavior over which another part had no control or much knowledge, which seems to me very related to the concepts of conscious and unconscious, *id*, *ego* and *superego*; in short, the basic elements present in Robert Louis Stevenson's novel seem to me to be intuitive "discoveries" of an artist, in a parallel situation, and in a social context similar to that of Dr. Freud's discoveries and theories.

In fact, I have the impression that, generally, when scientists who study human issues (including psychoanalysis, which, despite having been proposed as a "natural" science, focused on the study of human beings) come to formulate theories that impact the academic world, some artist has probably already created a work on the subject, even if, of course, without academic rigor and method, even if only in outline. When Marx created theories to make social denunciations that he considered "scientific," there were already literary works with similar denunciations before him; when Peter Berger and Thomas Luckmann, in Sociology, published their classic "The Social Construction of Reality," notions present there were already suggested

in works of literature that had existed for centuries, such as Miguel de Cervantes' denunciations of the capacity of novels themselves to induce figures like Don Quixote to behave according to pathetic beliefs, or in works not so earlier, such as the short story "The Alienist," by Brazilian writer Machado de Assis, showing how the concept of mental sanity is subject to being socially constructed; and when Dr. Freud began to give rigorous treatment to the concepts of the Unconscious, *id*, *superego*, and *ego*, the hidden side of Dr. Jekyll (Mr. "Hyde"/Hidden) already foreshadowed the concept of social repression, *superego*, overflow and realization of impulses, *id*; Ultimately, what strikes me most is not the "coincidences," but the fact that I rarely find mention of these similarities between the literary work in question and Freud's.

In my view, Robert Louis Stevenson's work is extremely "Freudian," one could say "ahead of its time." However, it's common to reject this epithet, since, in his own way, the author did what his time allowed him to do. But how can we understand this intuitive foreshadowing? In a way, I think Freud's own work provides the answer, since, by drawing on myths and literary works from the ancient Greek world, he illustrates how certain concepts were already (re)veiled in these works by artists before being (re)discovered and analyzed rationally – and not intuitively – by his new approach, now academic, with rigor, comprehensiveness, and a verifiable and apprehensible method through intellectual discipline.

This duplicity of one side of the mind that tends to want to satisfy instinctual needs – the *id* – but at the same time is subject to social demands to repress some of these tendencies – through the *superego* – and the result of this confrontation in an *ego* are present in other stories, such as the man who becomes a werewolf, or Dr. Bruce Banner who becomes the Hulk, and even Dr. Watson – Sherlock Holmes's assistant – who, in Jô Soares's novel, "The Xangô of Baker Street," catches a Pomba Gira. It's an element commonly explored in literature, but it seems to me that the work in which a similarity with elements of Freud's work became clearest was in Robert Louis Stevenson's "Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Jekyll."